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Review Article

NEEDLESTICK INJURIES AMONG HEALTH WORKERS IN SAUDI ARABIAAbdulelah Mohammed Alqarni¹, Ahmad Awadh Alatawi², Mohammed Hamad Alrashedi³, Meshal Saleh Alatawi⁴, Mohammed Ahmed Alhejaily⁵

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Abstract**Background**

Needle stick injuries (NSIs) are serious occupational hazards in the transmission of a variety of blood borne pathogens such as hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus (AIDS) among healthcare workers (HCWs). NSI is a common event in the health-care environment and these injuries may occur not only with freshly contaminated sharps, but also with needles that carry dry blood.

Objectives

In this study, we aim to: report on previous literature on NSIs that were carried out in Saudi Arabia and worldwide and detect the prevalence, causes and complications of NSIs.

Methods

PubMed database and EBSCO Information Services were used for articles selection. All relevant articles to our review with the topics regarding NSIs have been used. We excluded other articles, which are not related to this field. The data will be extracted according to specific form in which it is going to be reviewed by the group members.

Conclusion

Prevention of NSI is the best way to prevent several diseases in health care workers. It should be an integral part of prevention programs in the work place, and training of HCWs regarding safety practices indispensably needs to be an ongoing activity at the hospital. It is recommended that every hospital should develop a multi-pronged strategy to deal with NSI. Besides health promotion, there should be setting up of an adequate surveillance mechanism in every large hospital and also of facilities for prompt response and treatment of NSI.

Keywords: Needlestick, Injuries, Health Workers, Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Needle stick injuries (NSIs) are serious occupational hazards in the transmission of a variety of blood borne pathogens such as hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus (AIDS) among healthcare workers (HCWs) [1, 2]. Medical, dental, nursing, and midwifery workers are at high risk for occupational exposure to blood-borne pathogens (BBPs) via sharp injuries such as needle stick injuries [3]. Nurses have the highest rate of NSI among health-care workers [4]. NSIs are a common event in the health-care environment and these injuries may occur not only with freshly contaminated sharps, but also with needles that carry dry blood [5]. Injuries may be caused by objects such as hypodermic needles, blood collection needles, intravenous (IV) stylets and needles used to connect parts of IV delivery systems [6]. There is some evidence revealing a high prevalence of unsafe injection practices among HCWs in developing countries, where about 90% of accidents related to NSIs occur [7]. In a survey of 806 interventional radiology physicians, it was reported that, only half of the physicians exposed to needlestick injury; and the survey was not aimed for evaluation of the reporting practices [8].

In another study of 895 interventional radiologists, 91% of them reported a prior needlestick injury, 35% reported at least one injury during treatment of HIV-positive patient. Only 71% received training courses on needlestick injury. On the other hand, only 66% of injuries were reported [9]

OBJECTIVES:

In this study, we aim to: report on previous literature on NSIs that were carried out in Saudi Arabia and

worldwide and detect the prevalence, causes and complications of NSIs.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:**Sample & Study Groups**

PubMed and EBSCO Information Services were chosen as the search databases for the publications used within the study, as they are high-quality sources. PubMed being one of the largest digital libraries on the internet developed by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) which is a part of the United States National Library of Medicine. Topics concerning NSIs have been used in the making of the article. Restrictions to the last 10 years, country restriction on Saudi Arabia, and English language due to unavailable resources for translation were used. The founded articles were screened by titles, and reviewing the abstracts yielded 4 articles which were enrolled. Inclusion criteria: the articles were selected based on the relevance to the project which should include one of the following topics; 'NSIs, Occupational problems for nurses, NSIs among nurses'. Exclusion criteria: all other articles which did not have one of these topics as their primary end, or repeated studies, and reviews studies have been excluded.

Statistical Analysis

No software has been utilized to analyze the data. The data was extracted based on specific form that contains (Title of the publication, author's name, objective, summary, results, and outcomes). These data were reviewed by the group members to determine the initial findings, and the modalities of performing the surgical procedure. Double revision of each member's outcomes was applied to ensure the validity and minimize the mistakes.

RESULTS:

Table 1. Study, study design, country, objective, duration, outcome, and reference number

Study	Study Design	Country	Objective	Duration of Study	Outcome	Ref.
Khabour, Omar F et al.	survey-based study design	Al-Madinah, Saudi Arabia.	To examine self-reported frequency of occupational infection and needlestick injury among the clinical laboratory workers	-	The results showed that approximately 33% of the sample had an experienced occupational infection while 24% had experienced a needlestick injury. Occupational infection, needlestick injury and recapping needles after use were associated with lack of training on biosafety ($P < 0.05$).	10
Amini, Maryam et al.	cross-sectional, analytical and descriptive study	Tehran, Iran	to determine the rate of NSIs in a teaching hospital in Tehran, Iran.	-	only 50.2% of injuries had been reported; 67.8% of all participants (n = 211) had at least one NSI. Most participants mentioned the injection syringe needles as the main cause of their injuries (71.1% of all NSIs). Among NSIs, those caused by insulin syringe needles (6.2%) were the second cause.	11

Mohammad Hassan Kazemi Galougahi	Descriptive analytical cross-sectional study	Khanevadeh Hospital in Tehran	To evaluate prevalence of NSI in nursing workers of Tehran Khanevadeh Hospital and identify related factors in order to decrease the risk of infectious diseases transmission.	1 Year	About 40.5% of all participants were men and 59.5% were women. Mean age was 33.26 (8.03) years; 56.96% of participants had history of at least one needle stick injury and 22.15% of them had needle stick injury during last year. Injections were the most common action resulted to exposure (24.44%) and recapping of needles was at the second order (21.11%). Operation room had the highest prevalence (18.9%) of needle stick injuries among all wards of hospital.	12
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Trayner K. et al	cross-sectional survey	The 2017 British Dental Association (BDA) Conference and Exhibition in Manchester, and at the 2017 BDA Scottish Conference and Exhibition in Glasgow.	To estimate the prevalence of sharps injuries, the level of underreporting and of self-reported access to an OH service both for the care of sharps injuries and for general health and wellbeing.	5 years	A total of 796 delegates participated, of whom 166 (20.8%) had experienced a sharps injury in the past year and 58 (35%) did not report the incident. Of the participants, 190 (23.9%) reported no, or uncertain, access to OH support.	13
Alghamdi MS	cross-sectional study	King Abdulaziz University Hospital, Saudi Arabia	To identify predisposing factors of sustaining sharp injuries in operating rooms among surgical residents and their attitudes and behaviors in dealing with sharp injuries.	2 months	Among the 78 recruited residents, 46 (58.9%) had sharp injuries during surgical procedures. Most of the injuries (60%) were self-induced, and (72.9%) of the injuries took place while suturing. Twenty (43.5%) of those who had injuries did not report any injury, 15 (32.6%) reported some, and 11 (23.9%) claim that they reported all their sharp injuries. 44.9% of the participants are fully aware of sharp injuries local policy and procedures in the hospital. Most of the injured participants during surgeries did not follow each step of the local sharp injury policy. The perceived causes of sharp injuries among the participants were due to rushed (61.1%), fatigue (43%), lack of skills (19.4%), lack of assistance (15.3%), lack of sleep (13.9%) and (16.7%) though it is not preventable.	14

Yi Y	cross-sectional study	Hunan Province, China	To assess adherence behaviors for self-reporting of occupational exposure to blood and body fluids among RNs and identify factors affecting self-reporting	-	In total, 548 RNs completed the questionnaire. All participants experienced sharp object injuries at least once during their career; 65.88% of participants were exposed to blood/body fluids thrice, and 31.2% experienced 1–5 occupational exposures in the past month. However, only 14.6% of participants submitted a blood/body fluid exposure report to a supervisor/official after every incident. Blood/body fluid exposure was associated with the non-usage of safety protocols.	15
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Jaybhaye R. et al	cross-sectional study	India	To determine prevalence of needle stick injuries among health care workers. (2) To study circumstances under which they occur among health care workers in tertiary care hospital	-	A total 130 (59.09%) HCWs reported having occupational exposure to blood and body fluid in last one year, out of these 108 (49.09%) had NSIs and 22 (10%) had history of splash of blood and body fluid. Maximum exposure of NSIs was found among nurses (50%), followed by resident doctors (25.93%).	16
Baghcheghi N	descriptive cross-sectional study	Arak, University of Medical Sciences	To describe the frequency, causes and practice of nursing students in contaminated needle stick/sharps injuries.	-	70% and 43% of the subjects had experienced at least one contaminated NSIs in total education period and the past 12 months, respectively. The average number of injuries per student was 1.02 times/student/year. Approximately 40 percent of the injuries were not reported to the clinical educator. The first action after incidents in 51.6 % of the subjects was squeezing the wound. After incidents, 64.22 % tracking patients' tests for blood-borne pathogens and 10% of the subjects did not perform any action following incidents.	17
Salelkar S	cross-sectional study	Goa, India	To study the problem of needle stick injuries. A structured questionnaire was used to interview the study participants at their work place.	3 months	Around 34.8% (200/575) of the Health care workers had experienced a needle stick injury in the last one year. Needle stick injuries were equally distributed across different work experience periods. Hollow bore needles were responsible for 77.5% of needle stick injuries followed by suturing needles (19.2%). As far as use of personal protection was concerned only 58% of the health care workers were wearing gloves at the time of the injury.	18

DISCUSSION:

Needle stick injuries are one of the hidden problems in the health care workers [19]. The prevalence of NSIs in Bagdey et al study [20] (31.78%) was similar with Kulkarni MS et al [21], Mehta A et al [22], Karbaksh M et al [23] while Jayant S et al [24], Tetali S et al [25] and Khader Y et al [26] found higher prevalence of NSI in their studies. The incidence of NSIs among a sample including 180 nursing workers in a university hospital in Shahroud, Iran [26] was 114 cases (63.3%). Similarly, in Egypt of 273/371 nurses (62.3%) reported at least one NSI in the previous 12 months [27]. Also, the study of Jaybhaye R. et al revealed that Maximum exposure of NSIs was found among nurses (50%) [16] Furthermore, among 526 nurses and midwives in Uganda [7], the incidence of NSIs in the last year was 300 cases (57%).

(23.9%) of the participants at the 2017 (BDA) Conference and Exhibition in Manchester, and at the 2017 BDA Scottish Conference and Exhibition in Glasgow reported no, or uncertain, access to OH

support [13], also most of the injured participants during surgeries at Alghamdi MS study in King Abdulaziz University Hospital did not follow each step of the local sharp injury policy [14] Peculiarly, only 14.6% of participants in Yi Y study submitted a blood/body fluid exposure report to a supervisor/official after every incident [15], also Baghcheghi N showed that Approximately 40 percent of the injuries were not reported to the clinical educator [17], furthermore Salelkar S study revealed that only 58% of the health care workers were wearing gloves at the time of the injury [18]

The majority (51.8%) of injuries that occurred after use and before disposal of the objects [38] was similar to other findings [28]. Anjum et al. study [29] showed that; most injuries 59.4% occur while wearing single pair of gloves only 21.9% with double pair of gloves thus our study validates these studies and also the AORN's recommendations. In our study 96.9% items causing NSIs have no safety design. An Australian study concluded introduction of self-

retracting safety syringes and elimination of butterfly needles should reduce the current hollow-bore NSI by more than 70% and almost halve the total incidence of NSI [30].

Previous studies have shown increased risk of clinical laboratory workers to diverse types of infection from their work places [31] that include blood borne pathogens (HBV, HCV, HIV), respiratory illnesses (MERS-CoV, influenza viruses, Tuberculosis) [32] and skin infections [33]. In a cross-sectional survey study that was conducted in clinics from 10 Moroccan cities, 58.9% of the subjects underwent at least one occupational blood exposure [34]. The results showed an association between occupational infection and college degree holders and training on biosafety.

Immediate reporting of NSIs plays a vital role in post exposure prophylaxis and treatment of the injury. However, a number of researches have indicated a poor reporting rate of NSI incidents in healthcare settings, even in institutions with well-established sharps injury surveillance programs and easily accessible reporting systems [35]. The data of a Germanic university hospital, where a specialist consultant in emergency medicine is responsible for reporting occupational accidents and post exposure prophylaxis, showed that only 28.7% of injured HCWs reported the NSI. Moreover, recent evidence from some of the previous Asian investigations showed underreporting rates of NSIs in healthcare professions to be 76.2% in Thailand [36] and 99.3% in Pakistan [37].

CONCLUSION:

Prevention of NSI is the best way to prevent several diseases in health care workers. It should be an integral part of prevention programs in the work place, and training of HCWs regarding safety practices indispensably needs to be an ongoing activity at the hospital. It is recommended that every hospital should develop a multi-pronged strategy to deal with NSI. Besides health promotion, there should be setting up of an adequate surveillance mechanism in every large hospital and also of facilities for prompt response and treatment of NSI.

REFERENCES:

1. Wicker S., Jung J., Allwinn R., Gottschalk R., Rabenau H.F. Prevalence and prevention of needlestick injuries among health care workers in a German university hospital. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health.* 2008;81:347–354.
2. Lum D, Mason Z, Meyer-Rochow G, Neveldsen GB, Siriwardena M, Turner P, et al. Needle stick

- injuries in country general practice. *N Z Med J.* 1997;110(1041):122–5.
3. Askarian M, Malekmakan L. The prevalence of needle stick injuries in medical, dental, nursing and midwifery students at the university teaching hospitals of Shiraz, Iran. *Indian J Med Sci.* 2006;60(6):227–32.
4. ICN on preventing needle stick injuries. *Nursing matters: Fact sheets 2009.* Available from: http://www.medicalkenya.co.ke/2011/02nursing_matters_who_fac_sheet.
5. Cardo DM, Culver DH, Ciesielski CA, Srivastava PU, Marcus R, Abiteboul D, et al. A case-control study of HIV seroconversion in health care workers after percutaneous exposure. Centers for disease control and prevention needlestick surveillance group. *N Engl J Med* 1997;337:1485-90.
6. NIOSH. Preventing needlestick injuries in health care settings. U.S. Department of health and human services. Cincinnati: DHHS (NIOSH) publication; 1999.
7. Nsubuga F.M., Jaakkola M.S. Needle stick injuries among nurses in sub-Saharan Africa. *Trop Med Int Health.* 2005;10:773–781.
8. Hansen ME, Miller GL, 3rd, Redman HC, McIntire DD. HIV and interventional radiology: a national survey of physician attitudes and behaviors. *J Vasc Interv Radiol* 1993;4(2):229–236.
9. Baffoy-Fayard N, Maugat S, Sapoval M, et al. Potential exposure to hepatitis C virus through accidental blood contact in interventional radiology. *J Vasc Interv Radiol* 2003;14(2 Pt 1):173–179.
10. Khabour OF, Al Ali KH, Mahallawi WH. Occupational infection and needle stick injury among clinical laboratory workers in Al-Madinah city, Saudi Arabia. *J Occup Med Toxicol.* 2018;13:15. Published 2018 May 21. doi:10.1186/s12995-018-0198-5
11. Amini, Maryam et al. “Needle-Stick Injuries Among Healthcare Workers in a Teaching Hospital” *Trauma monthly* vol. 20,4 (2015): e18829.
12. “Evaluation of needle stick injuries among nurses of Khanevadeh Hospital in Tehran” *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research* vol. 15,4 (2010): 172-7.
13. K. M. A. Trayner, L. Hopps, M. Nguyen, M. Christie, J. Bagg et al. Cross-sectional survey of a sample of UK primary care dental professionals' experiences of sharps injuries and perception of access to occupational health support. *British Dental Journal.* Nov 30, 2018
14. Alghamdi MS, Abbas MM, Shafei MO, Alali

- AM, Alshareef MA, Aljabri FA, Zaidi NH, Aljiffry MM. Sharp injuries in the operative room among residents in surgical specialties: A cross-sectional study. *Saudi Surg J* 2018;6:11-5
15. Yi Y, Yuan S, Li Y, Mo D, Zeng L (2018) Assessment of adherence behaviors for the self-reporting of occupational exposure to blood and body fluids among registered nurses: A cross-sectional study. *PLoS ONE* 13(9): e0202069.
 16. Devendra R Jaybhaye, Prashant L Dahire, Ajit S Nagaonkar, Vinod L Vedpathak, Deepali S Deo, Umesh G Kawalkar. Needle stick injuries among health care workers in tertiary care hospital in tertiary care hospital of rural India. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2014; 3(1): 49-52. doi: 10.5455/ijmsph.2013.230920133
 17. Baghcheghi N, Koohestani H, rezaei K, seraji A, Abedi A. Prevalence needlestick/sharps injuries among nursing student and related factor . *ioh*. 2011; 7 (4) :6-0
 18. Salelkar S, Motghare D D, Kulkarni M S, Vaz F S. Study of needle stick injuries among health care workers at a tertiary care hospital. *Indian J Public Health* 2010;54:18-20
 19. Mehta A, Rodrigues C, Singhal T, Lopes N,D'Souza N, Sathe K, Dastur FD. Interventions to reduce needle stick injuries at a tertiary care centre. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2010;28(1):17–20.
 20. Bagdey et al. NEEDLE STICK INJURIES AMONG STAFF NURSES IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL OF CENTRAL INDIA. *ASIAN PACIFIC JOURNAL OF HEALTH SCIENCES*, 2014; 1(3):149-154
 21. Kulkarni, M. S., Salelkar, S., Motghare, D. D., & Vaz, F. S. Study of needle stick injuries among health care workers at a tertiary care hospital. *Indian journal of public health* 2010;54(1):18.
 22. Mehta A, Rodrigues C, Singhal T, Lopes N, D'Souza N, Sathe K, Dastur FD. Interventions to reduce needle stick injuries at a tertiary care centre. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2010;28(1):17–
 23. Jayanth, S. T., Kirupakaran, H., Brahmadathan, K. N., Gnanaraj, L., & Kang, G. Needle stick injuries in a tertiary care hospital. *Indian journal of medical microbiology* 2009; 27(1):44-48
 24. Gupta A, Shuchi A, sastry J, Karigar A, Baswaraj A, Gupte N, High risk for occupational exposure to HIV and utilization of post exposure prophylaxis in a teaching hospital in Pune, India, *BMC infectious Diseases* 2008;8:142-51.
 25. Khader, Y., S. Burgan, and Z. Amarin. "Self-reported needle-stick injuries among dentists in north Jordan." *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*; 2009:15.1
 26. Ebrahimi H., Khosravi A. Needlestick injuries among nurses. *J Res Health Sci*. 2007;7:56–62.
 27. Hanafi M., Mohamed A., Kassem M., Shawki M. Needlestick injuries among health care workers of University of Alexandria Hospitals. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2011;17:26–35.
 28. Jahan S. Epidemiology of needlestick injuries among health care workers in a secondary care hospital in Saudi Arabia. *Ann Saudi Med*. 2005; 25(3):233-38.
 29. Hashmi A, Al Reesh SA, Indah L (2012) Prevalence of Needle-stick and Sharps Injuries among Healthcare Workers, Najran, Saudi Arabia. *Epidemiol* 2:117. doi: 10.4172/2161-1165.1000117
 30. Whitby RM, McLaws ML (2002) Hollow-bore needle stick injuries in a tertiary teaching hospital: epidemiology, education and engineering. *Med J Aust* 177: 418-422.
 31. Adams D. Needlestick and sharps injuries: practice update. *Nurs Stand*. 2012;26:49–57. doi: 10.7748/ns.26.24.49.s54..
 32. Wilburn SQ. Needlestick and sharps injury prevention. *Online J Issues Nurs*. 2004;9:5.
 33. Wei Q, Li XY, Wang L, et al. Preliminary studies on pathogenic microorganisms laboratory-acquired infections cases in recent years and its control strategies. *Zhnghua Shi Yan He Lin Chuang Bing Du Xue Za Zhi*. 2011;25:390–392.
 34. Laraqui O, Laraqui S, Tripodi D, et al. Assessing knowledge, attitude, and practice on occupational blood exposure in caregiving facilities, in Morocco. *Med Mal Infect*. 2008;38:658–666. doi: 10.1016/j.medmal.2008.09.009.
 35. Henderson D.K. Management of needlestick injuries: a house officer who has a needlestick. *JAMA*. 2012;307:75–84.
 36. Honda M., Chompikul J., Rattanapan C., Wood G., Klungboonkrong S. Sharps injuries among nurses in a Thai regional hospital: prevalence and risk factors. *Int J Occup Environ Med*. 2011;2:215–223.
 37. Habib H., Khan E.A., Aziz A. Prevalence and factors associated with needle stick injuries among registered nurses in public sector tertiary care hospitals of Pakistan. *Int J Collab Res Intern Med Public Health*. 2011;3:124–130.
 38. H. Ebrahimi, A. Khosravi. Needlestick injuries among nurses. *J Res Health Sci*, 7 (2007), pp. 56-62